

Teaching Notes for the paper:

Using AI Personas for Requirements Engineering: A Teaching Case

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Submitted at Journal of Systems and Software: Special Issue on Teaching Cases
in Software Engineering

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Introduction

The teaching case introduces an approach for integrating AI Personas into higher education to support the teaching and learning of requirements engineering practices. As generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) continues to reshape academic instruction, the case provides instructors with a practical and learning-objective-oriented method for embedding GenAI into coursework without depending on a specific large language model, tool, or technical setup.

Designed with a modular structure, the case guides students through the elicitation, evaluation, and documentation of requirements using AI-based stakeholder simulations by means of AI personas (see Fig.1). Its flexible design allows instructors to adapt the case to diverse teaching formats and disciplinary contexts. Drawing on repeated implementations over several semesters in different courses and degree programs, the case offers a pedagogically grounded way to incorporate GenAI into higher education teaching, preparing students for contemporary and future software engineering practices.

Figure 1: Applied Teaching Case

Below, we provide details of two specific teaching notes. The first teaching note describes the application and customization of the teaching case “*Using AI Personas for Requirements Engineering*” for the Project Management module in the online Bachelor’s of Science program in Business Informatics at University of Applied Sciences Emden/Leer. The second application of the teaching case was performed in the Requirements Analysis module in a Bachelor of Science program in Business Information Systems at University of Applied Sciences and Arts Hannover.

1. HS Emden/Leer: Overview and Synopsis

The teaching case was implemented during the winter semester 2025/2026 at the University of Applied Sciences Emden/Leer. An overview of the instructional setting and implementation conditions is provided in Table 1.

Topic	Description
Degree program	Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.), Business Informatics (online degree program)
Module	Project Management
Learning Objectives of Module	The students are able to plan, manage, and control a project (particularly a software project)
Students	The group size is 20 students. Many students work in the business sector. The program is designed so that it can be completed while working.
Implementation of Teaching Case	The teaching case is implemented as a semester-long exercise; students must complete and pass three assignments in order to be admitted to the exam.
Duration of case	Three assignments to be completed in groups of 2, each with an online meeting to discuss the assignments in plenary.
Term of application	Winter term 2025/2026

Table 1: Synopsis of real-world application of the teaching case at HS Emden

1.1 Topics, Key Issues, and Case Questions

For the application of the teaching case in this module, a customization was carried out to adapt both the case study and the associated exercise and discussion and reflection. The learning material can be provided upon request. Please send your request via e-mail to: eva-maria.schoen@hs-emden-leer.de. The case study was developed based on the following narrative:

Implementing AI Agents in Higher Education

As part of a project aimed at supporting teaching, learning, and administrative processes, a university plans to introduce AI agents. The goal is to advance digital transformation within the higher education context, increase process efficiency, and improve the user experience for students, instructors, and staff. At the same time, both the opportunities and the risks of such an implementation are to be critically assessed. The introduction of AI agents at the university involves several target groups: students, instructors, and staff (e.g., administration/service units, IT). These groups have different needs that must be considered in the solution design.

- Conduct a product discovery and apply the agile practices of personas and story maps.
- Perform agile effort estimation and planning, application of agile practices: magic estimation, release planning using story maps, and Minimum Viable Product (MVP)
- Understand risk management using control variables and project management metrics, conduct risk analysis, and develop a risk management strategy

The students received three separate worksheets for the implementation. In addition, references (videos and literature) were provided to help them understand the technical concepts through self-study so that they could then apply them in the tasks. Students worked in groups of two to complete the assignments and submit their solutions via a learning management system. The instructor evaluated the solutions and provided feedback. The assessment was based on a pass or fail system. The solutions were then discussed during online sessions, which also provided an opportunity for discussion and reflection.

1.2 Learning Objectives

In addition to the learning objectives mentioned in the teaching case, the following learning objectives were added for the three worksheets:

- Conducting a product discovery to plan a (software) project and learn how to use techniques and tools.
- Performing agile effort estimation and planning to plan a (software) project and learn how to use techniques and tools.

- Understanding risk management using project management controls and metrics to ensure transparency regarding project progress.

1.3 Prompts for Customization of the Teaching Case

The modular approach of the teaching case allows for quick adaptation of the three components: AI Personas, exercise, and discussion and reflection using GenAI. In the following, the initial prompts that were used for the customization in this case are listed. The GenAI-generated output was refined in several iterations before we adapted it manually.

- A new semester is coming up. As a professor for the Project Management module in the Bachelor's degree program in Online Business Informatics, I want to create a new case study. I will give you a text to read that contains last semester's case study. This will serve as the template for the new case study. Please analyze the text and let me know when you are done.
- The new case study will focus on the topic of "The use of AI agents in a higher education institution." The target groups of the agent system are students, teachers, and staff. I have some information about AI agents that discusses their advantages and disadvantages. Please add an additional section to the document in which you add the individual statements in a table.
- In the past, I used an AI chatbot to enable students to conduct interviews with stakeholders on a different topic. Please rewrite the meta prompt/config file to include the content of the new case study (target groups and use cases/AI agents). The meta prompt should enable students to conduct interviews with the target group and ask questions about the requirements for AI agents. The meta prompt is already quite old. Please optimize it for current LLMs. Here is the old meta prompt that needs to be updated: (see meta-prompt in teaching case)

1.4 Implementation Guidance for Using the Case

In the following, we would like to provide further information for instructors so that the teaching case can be applied.

Preparation of teaching materials

At the beginning of the semester, the material can be customized. The prompts can be found in Section 1.3. For this teaching note, we prepared the following:

- Case study description
- Three separate worksheets for the assignments
- Additional material with templates for the agile practices and further references to explain the practices that are used in the assignments
- Meta prompt for the simulation of the stakeholder interviews
- Video that demonstrates how a meta prompt can be used with a GenAI tool like ChatGPT or GenAI tools provided by the University
- A slide deck that guides through the discussion and reflection sessions after submission of the assignments

Procedure during the semester

The three assignments were released via the learning management system over the course of the semester. The groups of two had one month to complete each assignment. The solutions were then submitted via the learning management system and evaluated by the instructor. After the students received feedback on their solutions, an online chat took place to discuss the results and critical pitfalls, as well as ethical aspects of using GenAI.

Technical implementation notes

In the past, we provided AI Personas as customized GPT via ChatGPT. This had some limitations, such as restrictions on the number of prompts due to licensing, and some students wanted to use regionally operated LLMs due to privacy concerns. Therefore, we decided to provide the application via a meta prompt. We recommend the usage of a meta prompt because of the experienced limitations.

1.7 Students feedback

To evaluate our teaching case, we created a short survey for students to complete after submitting their first assignment. Unfortunately, only seven students completed the survey, so we will not include a statistical analysis here as the results are not meaningful due to the small sample size. The survey also included open-ended

questions. The students' feedback is presented below (translated from German to English using DeepL).

Question: What did you like about the simulation, and what should be kept the same?

- *“The specification of the meta prompt is, of course, important. Furthermore, I found that working in pairs was appropriate in terms of time.”*
- *“The basic design of the simulation is very well done, and the actual process of collecting qualitative user data was taught much better than in a normal research project, as it helped participants understand that information can be gathered from the users themselves, rather than from above through research.”*
- *“It is generally a good method for simulating conversations with real people. Overall, it reinforces the practical relevance.”*
- *“The expression and information content were very good.”*
- *“AI has already become very good thanks to the state of the art. I am interested in the technology, but I don't necessarily want to use it.”*

Question: What did you dislike about the simulation? Please suggest improvements for the simulation (if any).

- *“The AI is far too easily led in certain directions, merely following the conversation rather than shaping it. It is logical that AI has no personality, but this ultimately changes the context of the situation. It felt less like a conversation and more like “fishing” for information.”*
- *“The use of AI should be taught as part of the degree program. However, I believe that AI should not be the main component of the project management module. Personally, I would prefer to see the content of project management taught in the traditional way (lectures), as I believe this would lead to better learning outcomes.”*

We received further feedback in the reflection and discussion session. The session was recorded, and we summarized the feedback from students in the following:

- *“I found using the chatbot very interesting. I had never used it in this way before.”*

- *“I am someone who learns best through hands-on experience. That’s why I find the assessment important for me to know whether I can apply the knowledge in practice.”*
- *“The interview was quite nice. The AI was very talkative and almost forced me to move on to the next one. The questions for the AI had to be well formulated; otherwise, it would only have answered very briefly with yes or no.”*

2. HS Hannover: Overview and Synopsis

The teaching case was applied during the 2024/2025 winter semester at the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Hannover. An overview of the instructional setting and implementation conditions is presented in Table 2.

Topic	Description
Degree programs	Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Information Systems (BIS) • E-Government (EGOV)
Module	Requirements Analysis (3 rd term of studies)
Learning Objectives of Module	The students are able to analyze requirements for software products by applying object oriented paradigm using Unified Modeling Language.
Students	The group size is around 65 students for BIS and 30 students for EGOV. The students have diverse background in term of profession and school examina.
Implementation of Teaching Case	The teaching case is implemented as an impulse workshop. The attendance to the workshop is not mandatory.
Duration of case	The workshop is planned for 90 minutes.
Term of application	Winter term 2024/2025

Table 2: Synopsis of real-world application of the teaching case at HS Hannover

2.1 Topics, Key Issues, and Case Questions

For the application of the teaching case in this module, a customization was carried out to adapt both the case study and the associated exercise and discussion and reflection. The learning material can be provided upon request. Please send your request via e-mail to: michael.neumann@hs-hannover.de. The case study was developed based on the following narrative:

Implementing AI Agents in Higher Education

As part of a teaching case implemented in the winter semester 2024/2025 at the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Hannover, students were trained to elicit and analyze requirements for a mobile public administration app. The objective was to prepare prospective requirements engineers to work with different user types and to understand the challenges of digital transformation in the public sector. The scenario focused on typical citizen services, such as applying for identity documents or registering a change of residence, while reflecting the scepticism and change-resistance often found in public administrations. At the same time, the involved stakeholders were intrinsically motivated to support the requirements engineer and provide realistic requirements.

Students conducted elicitation sessions with three predefined stakeholders representing different user perspectives: A public administration specialist, an accessibility-focused citizen, and a power user from a large city. Each stakeholder provided concise requirements for an appointment booking feature, expressed preferences, and occasionally showed resistance by posing counter questions or referencing failed app functions from well-known administrations. The students were expected to respond empathetically, stay within the defined project context, and steer the conversation back to the elicitation goal when needed.

Students applied various elicitation methods (e.g., interviews, focus groups), analyzed the resulting requirements, and documented them in user story format in a product backlog. The exercise enabled them to practice realistic stakeholder communication, handle conflicting expectations, and translate elicited information into structured agile requirements.

2.2 Learning Objectives

In addition to the learning objectives mentioned in the teaching case (see Section 2 in the teaching case), the following learning objectives were defined:

- Conducting user story creation and experience the work with GenAI tools like ChatGPT.
- Priorization techniques for user stories and backlogs.

2.3 Customization of the Teaching Case

We provide a customized GPT (via OpenAI ChatGPT) to the students based on the following scheme/configuration:

Objective

Challenge and train the user (prospective requirements engineer) to deal with different user types for a mobile application, which we have to build.

Context

The context of the mobile app is for a public administration in Germany. The mobile app should provide functionalities for citizen-oriented services like applying for identity documents, re-registering your place of residence when you move, issuing birth certificates, registering weddings, and much more. The chatbot should be equipped with the background knowledge that public administrations often face resistance to change by providing such mobile applications or online functionalities for their citizens. Employees are interested in the mobile app project, even if they are a bit sceptical. However, the stakeholders have an intrinsic motivation to provide realistic and correct requirements for the app and support the requirements engineer (your user) in requirements gathering.

Approach

Listen to the question asked by the user and act as one of the three end users from the mobile application: Stakeholder 1 (Public Administration Specialist): Larissa Müller (Administrative assistant at the local government of Musterstadt); Stakeholder 2 (User 1) Herbert Pfeiffer (Citizen of a small community; he focuses on accessibility, readability, and ease of use.) Stakeholder 3 (User 3) Ben Kampinski (Citizen of a large city; someone who uses many functions and needs deep functionality and customization options.) Larissa Müller gives precise and short answers for the requirements of a calendar/appointment booking feature in the app. Herbert Pfeiffer gives precise and short answers for the requirements of a calendar/appointment booking feature in the app. Ben Kampinski gives precise and short answers for the requirements of a calendar/appointment booking feature in the app. All three stakeholders favor the online appointment management functionality

in the mobile app and give this requirement as the first answer when the user asks them. Show sometimes resistance to the asked questions by posing counter-questions and citing specific examples of failed functions in mobile apps. Feel free to ask for more context or information. If you do not get this, examples from renowned public administrations (also international) are preferred to those from the past of one's own administration. If the user provides sensible questions, please provide specific requirements for such a mobile app. End the conversation either with acceptance of the change or the statement that you were not fully convinced.

Closer: "Thank you for the conversation. I am happy to support your mobile app development project and wish you and your team all the best. Looking forward to using your mobile app."

Communication style

Always stay within the context of requirements engineering and the mentioned project above, and do not deviate from the defined role. You act as one of the three mentioned stakeholders, and you are not to deviate from these roles. You do not moderate or ask further questions to your user. Pay attention to the user's feelings and emotions and adjust your approach accordingly. Be concise and to the point to make the conversation fluid and understandable for the user.

IMPORTANT

Stay on topic. Stay true to the instructions and the overall goal, and quickly bring conversations that deviate from the topic back to the original goal. End of training: The conversation ends when the objectives are sufficiently covered or when the user asks to end the conversation. Answer as briefly as possible. End with a summary and thank the user.

2.4 Implementation Guidance for Using the Case

In the following, we would like to provide further information for instructors so that the teaching case can be applied.

Preparation of teaching materials

At the beginning of the semester, the material can be customized. The customized GPT can be found above in Section 2.3. For this teaching note, we prepared the following:

- Case study description
- Meta-prompt and configuration file for the customized GPT model used to simulate stakeholder interviews.
- Slidedeck that guides through the discussion and reflection sessions after submission of the assignments

Procedure during the semester

We have organised a workshop at the end of the term. The workshop will last approximately 90 minutes. Participation is voluntary for students. They will receive the necessary information and tasks via a slide deck. Students without a ChatGPT Plus licence (who therefore have limited or no access to prompting) can participate in the workshop by using a meta prompt. The instructor will supervise students as they work through the teaching case, providing guidance and tips. The final 20–25 minutes will be reserved for reviewing the results and facilitating a discussion. Individual artefacts, such as user stories or backlogs, will be discussed, and difficulties and limitations will be addressed.

Technical implementation notes

In the past, we provided AI Personas as customized GPT via ChatGPT. This had some limitations, such as restrictions on the number of prompts due to licensing, and some students wanted to use regionally operated LLMs due to privacy concerns. Therefore, we decided to provide the application via a meta prompt. We recommend the usage of a meta prompt because of the experienced limitations.

2.5 Students feedback

As with the first applied teaching case (see above), we conducted a similar survey using the tool LimeSurvey to gain feedback from the students. The data was conducted in German, so we translated the student comments via DeepL into English. The n for this survey was 18.

Question: What did you like about the simulation, and what should be kept the same?

“Practical experience, concretization of user stories using real examples”

“The opportunity to practice case studies and thus learn in a realistic manner”

“Overall, the chatbot worked well and provided useful answers with good prompts.”

“Good practice example in requirements analysis (slicing, prioritization)”

Question: What did you dislike about the simulation? Please suggest improvements for the simulation (if any).

“Problems with prompt limitation in Chat GPT

“It is sometimes unclear how exactly to proceed in the first session (as a suggestion for improvement, check the status of all queries at 15-minute intervals and clarify what the next step would be).”

“Limitations of AI

Clearer work instructions (worksheet perhaps?)

Go into more detail about slicing / separate task?”

“I found the amount of work involved in creating user stories and refinement to be somewhat insufficient. I think it would be better conceptually to somehow establish a goal for why you are doing this:

For example, you could say that the task is to create user stories, work them out, and then, at the end, focus on one specific functionality and work it out in detail in terms of why this function is essential and how it improves everyday work or saves costs. At the end, everyone could then compile their findings and perhaps see other perspectives as a result.”